

IN-LINE PLASMA MODIFIED CARBON FIBRE FOR ENHANCED THERMOPLASTIC TAPE MANUFACTURING – REPURPOSING HARD TO RECYCLE WASTE IN NEW ZEALAND

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ABSTRACT

To meet increasing legislative demand for a circular plastics economy, novel technology is needed to produce high-performing composites from waste polymers. Introduced processes must be low-cost and environmentally friendly to be future proof. In this paper, a novel slot-channel melt impregnation tool was used to produce continuous carbon fibre (CF)-reinforced thermoplastic tapes with fewer processing steps than state-of-the-art powder and commingling processes. Process applicability was tested for polyamide 6 (PA6), PA6 blended with polypropylene (PP), and waste film linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE) containing PA6. For the first time, an atmospheric pressure plasma jet with air carrier gas was applied in-line to enhance the melt impregnated tapes. The slot-channel melt impregnation process operated more consistently with the active in-line plasma surface treatment as a result of improved fibre alignment and cohesion by pneumatic spreading. The slot-channel melt impregnator produced tapes with high degrees of impregnation for all matrix systems, irrespective of the reinforcement treatment. Compression moulded PA6 and PA6/PP (50:50 wt.%) matrix composite short beam strength significantly benefited from CF plasma surface treatment, increasing by 45.2% and 89.8%, respectively. The 36% increase of O/C elemental composition on the CF surface did not enhance PA6/LLDPE (20:80 wt.%) composite performance because the dominant dispersive matrix is incompatible with the polar fibre surface. The present work introduces a viable thermoplastic tape manufacturing process that can effectively impregnate dry fibres with as-received and shredded waste polymers. This process is especially promising because it significantly enhances tapes made with a PA6/PP matrix, a common hard-to-recycle blend that is currently not repurposed in New Zealand.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymeric waste is poorly utilised in New Zealand. Out of the estimated 45,000 tonnes of plastic collected for recycling annually, up to 90% are exported [1]. While large quantities of engineering thermoplastic such as nylon are available for reuse in municipal and post-industrial waste, they are usually considered as hard to recycle by council recycling schemes [2]. Consequently, clean recovery of polyamides is currently under prioritised, leading to potential contamination and phase separation of

waste thermoplastic with non-compatible polymers [3]. Such incompatibilities reduce the matrix strength [4] and compatibilisation between the fibre surface and multiple matrix constituents [5]. Despite the aforementioned concerns, technology to produce fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites with matrices containing waste polymer must be developed to meet the demand for a circular plastics economy. An appropriate issue to address is that 39% of plastics in Europe were converted to packaging in 2020 [6], necessitating processes that re-use polymeric film blends. This work investigates the feasibility of producing carbon fibre (CF)-reinforced thermoplastics constituting a blended polyamide 6 (PA6) matrix. Mixtures of PA6 with polypropylene (PP) or polyethylene (PE) are commonly found in hard-to-recycle packaging films.

Enhanced bonding between the incompatible CF-reinforcement and the blended matrix, without the use of wet chemical treatments, is of primary interest to align with the environmental motivations of this project. This paper instead presents a continuous air plasma functionalisation process to rapidly modify the CF surface for interface enhancement, similar to other works in the literature [7, 8, 9, 10]. Two novel contributions are presented in this work. Firstly, the integration of in-line plasma treatment with a novel slot-channel melt impregnation process is studied. Secondly, the process is used to elucidate the influence of plasma surface treatment on tape matrices constituting (i) PA6, (ii) PA6/PP made from virgin constituents to emulate the waste mixture, and (iii) waste PA6/PE film. Overall, issues encountered when processing continuous fibre-reinforced composites from hard-to-recycle waste polymers are demonstrated, and the performance enhancement by rapid in-line plasma modification is shown using the short beam strength test.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

Commercial high-strength, standard modulus polyacrylonitrile-based CFs were supplied unsized by Hyosung (Tansome H2550, Republic of Korea) as continuous 12K tows ($\text{tex} = 800 \text{ g.km}^{-1}$, filament diameter = $7 \mu\text{m}$, tensile modulus = 250 GPa, tensile strength = 5516 MPa, elongation = 2.2%, untwisted). Unsized CFs were utilised in this work to remove the complexity of size burn-off and degradation during surface treatment [11]. The virgin PA6 matrix used in this work was Ultramid B3S (BASF GmbH, Germany). Before compounding or melt impregnation, the hygroscopic PA6 was dried at 92°C for 24 h. The virgin polymer blend matrix, emulating a hard-to-recycle waste blend, admixed MOPLEN HP400N PP (LyondellBasell, USA) to the PA6. Waste polymer films were sourced from an Auckland, New Zealand-based recycling facility.

2.2 Continuous plasma surface treatment

The pulsed DC plasma source utilised in this continuous treatment was a Tantec-X PLX (Denmark) atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ) with an excitation frequency, power, and flow rate range of $\sim 40.4 \text{ kHz}$, 416 W and $1400\text{-}2500 \text{ L.h}^{-1}$, respectively. Figure 1 depicts the experimental setup for in-line plasma treatment. The fibre tow was let-off (2) from a bobbin and aligned with the plasma treatment zone (6). Vertically offset nitride-hardened 5 mm steel pins spread and tension the tow (5). The line-speed of 0.83 m.min^{-1} , yielding a good degree of impregnation, was controlled by a belt pulling unit prior to take-up on a winder. The working gas flow rate and fibre-nozzle distance used for tape manufacturing were 2200 L.h^{-1} , and 10 mm, respectively. The selection of these parameters is elucidated in Section 3.1 by optical emission spectroscopy (OES) and high-speed imaging.

Figure 1: Continuous APPJ treatment setup schematic to modify the CF surface in-line prior to melt impregnation.

2.3 Optical emission spectroscopy

OES was applied to inspect spatial and working gas flow rate trends of reactive species in the air plasma discharge. The optical emission spectrographs were acquired on an EPP2000 portable spectrometer (Stellarnet, USA) by targeting a fibre optic cable mounted to a three-axis micro-positioning table. Spatial emission variation was measured along the APPJ system line of axial symmetry with coordinates centred at the nozzle exit. Measurements were acquired for distances from 2 to 12.5 mm and working gas flow rates between 1400 and 2200 L.h⁻¹.

2.4 High-speed imaging

A VEO 410L (Phantom, USA) global shutter and mono sensor, high-speed camera equipped with a 105 mm Micro-NIKKOR (Nikon, Japan) lens was used to capture the plasma discharge at the nozzle exit. An exposure time, frame rate, aperture and exposure index of 490 μ s, 2000 fps, f/4 and 6400, respectively, were used to capture diffuse and filamentary discharge frames for nozzle-fibre distances between 6 and 12 mm.

2.5 X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

Functionality of the CF tow top surface was assessed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Samples were stuck on vacuum safe sticky tape immediately after plasma treatment to be placed in the XPS vacuum chamber, pumped down within 4 hours of the plasma treatment, and measured within 72 hours. The XPS measurements were acquired on an Axis Ultra (Kratos analytical, USA) using monochromatic Al K α X-rays with a power of 124 W. The survey and high-resolution scan pass energy was 160 and 20 eV, respectively. Elemental composition was calculated from the survey spectrum.

2.6 Polymer processing

The virgin polymer blend was melt-blended in a corotating twin screw extruder (Brabender, GER) with a diameter and length-to-diameter ratio of 20 mm and 40, respectively. Blends were extruded at a screw speed of 60 rpm and a downstream temperature profile of 190 – 200 – 210 – 220 – 230 – 240°C. Waste polymer film was shredded into flakes. The flakes were dried and directly used in the melt impregnation process. Filamentary extrusion to pelletise the waste polymer was avoided to minimise degradation and processing costs.

2.7 Differential scanning calorimetry

Polymer constituent mixtures were characterised by differential scanning calorimetry (Netzsch, DSC300 Caliris classic, Germany). All samples were annealed at 275 °C, and subsequent melting endotherms were measured between -25 and 275°C at a heating rate of 10°C.min⁻¹ in a nitrogen atmosphere.

2.8 Melt impregnation process

The impregnation die utilised in this work had a wavy geometry with a slot channel through which the fibre and polymer passed, as depicted in Figure 2a with a three-dimensional view in Figure 2b. The process is analogous to pin-driven impregnation in a melt chamber. Its difference lies in the small channel cross-section that develops elevated melt pressure. The impregnator was baselined on a non-vented 19/20 single-screw extruder (Brabender, Germany) that was flood-fed with dry PA6, PA6/PP, and shredded waste film. Samples made from as-received or plasma surface-treated reinforcement are identified as CF and pCF, respectively. After melt impregnation, the out-of-tool tape passed over two hot pins at 270°C (Figure 3) in order to post-consolidate and smoothen the tape surfaces.

Figure 2: (a) Schematic of the wavy slot channel cross-head thermoplastic melt impregnator. The skeleton drawing omits the thermal conductor jackets and the heater bands over the slot for clarity.

Image (b) illustrates the assembled tool including heater bands and instrumentation.

Figure 3: Images of (a) the instrumented cross-head melt impregnator and (b) the out-of-tool tape passing over two hot pins below the melt impregnator.

2.9 Cross-sectional microscopy

Tape quality was qualitatively inspected by microscopy. Out-of-tool and hot-pin post-consolidated tapes were mounted in Specifix-40 (Struers, Denmark), polished to a finish of $0.05\ \mu\text{m}$ and ultrasonically cleaned to remove contamination from pores. Cross-sectional micrographs were acquired on a DSX1000 (Olympus, Japan) digital microscope.

2.10 Mechanical characterization

After drying for 24 hours, the tapes were stacked in a 3 mm thick compression mould to produce samples for short beam strength testing according to ASTM D2344. The compression moulding temperature and compaction pressure were 280°C and 16 bar, respectively. The pre-heating and compression cycle times were 8 and 2 min, respectively. A 10-minute water cooling cycle reduced the mould temperature to 40°C . The diamond-cut unidirectional laminates ($18\ \text{mm} \times 6\ \text{mm} \times 3\ \text{mm}$) were environmentally conditioned prior to testing at room temperature and 50% relative humidity. At least five specimens were tested for each sample.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Plasma characteristics and carbon fibre surface modification

APPJs have a higher spatial heterogeneity compared to plasma devices with tubular or parallel plate electric field configurations. The spatial heterogeneity is presented in Figure 4 using OES data, where the maximum emission intensity of atomic oxygen exponentially decays with increasing distance from the nozzle exit. Critically, the emission intensity is more sensitive to position than the working gas flow rate.

Figure 4: Optical emission spectroscopy logarithmic maximum emission intensity of the 777 nm atomic oxygen band for varying working gas flow rate. The longitudinal measurement point along the APPJ centre line was measured with respect to the nozzle exit.

Since emission intensity is proportional to species density, the logarithmic decay from Figure 4 suggests that the CF tow should pass through the APPJ treatment zone with a minimum nozzle-fibre distance for maximum exposure. However, the electrical conductivity of CFs disallows small nozzle-fibre distances. This is due to a transition from diffuse to filamentary plasma discharge when moving the fibre tow surface closer to the nozzle exit. Figure 5 illustrates the discharge mode transition behaviour for a fixed working gas flow rate of 1800 L.h⁻¹ at nozzle-fibre distances between 6 and 12 mm. It shows that distances beyond 10 mm yield diffuse plasma for the fixed flow rate. However, we have previously shown that the working gas flow rate also governs the discharge mode [12].

Figure 5: High speed camera frames of the APPJ interacting with the CF tow. The nozzle fibre distances for images (a) – (d) are 6, 8, 10, and 12 mm, respectively.

Fibre surface functionality after plasma treatment at a fixed distance and a fixed working gas flow rate is also a function of residence time [12]. Since the in-line plasma treatment residence time in this work is governed by the overall melt impregnation line speed, for the sake of brevity, surface functionality for varying line-speed is not presented. Instead, we show the as-received and plasma-treated CF surface functionality measured by XPS in Figure 6, where the line-speed, working gas flow rate and nozzle-fibre distance were 0.83 m.min⁻¹, 2200 L.h⁻¹, and 10 mm, respectively. Visually inspecting the C 1s band in Figure 6a gives the impression that the C-OH, C-O-C and C=O concentrations have increased after surface treatment. The O 1s peak in Figure 6b gives further evidence for an increase in R-O-R and -OH functionality. However, a similar increase in =O functionality is not observed, indicating that the C=O peak fitting of the C 1s peak may be subject to fitting error. Overall, the survey spectra reveal an O/C increase of 36%.

Figure 6: High-resolution XPS spectra of the (a) C 1s and the (b) O 1s band before and after plasma surface treatment. The line speed, working gas flow rate and nozzle-fibre distance were 0.83 m.min⁻¹, 2200 L.h⁻¹, and 10 mm, respectively.

3.2 Polymer mixture characterisation

DSC was used to detect the waste film composition. Table 1 summarises the peak melting temperatures of the various phases in each sample. The neat PA6 melting curve has a single peak at 220°C with a heat of fusion of 61.54 J.g⁻¹. Blending PA6 with PP adds a peak at 163°C with a heat of fusion of 50.73 J.g⁻¹. This confirms the 50:50 ratio in the blend, as the PA6 heat of fusion has been reduced by 52%. The waste film exhibits a similar PA6 melting peak at 220°C with a heat of fusion of 12.06 J.g⁻¹. Assuming that it has an equivalent heat of fusion as the neat PA6 Ultramid B3s, the PA6 mass fraction in the hard-to-recycle film is approximately 20%. Most of the hard-to-recycle film is linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE), as ascertained from the low-temperature melt peak at 128.9°C [13].

Table 1: PA6, PA6/PP and waste film DSC data

Sample	Peak temperature 1 [°C]	Peak temperature 2 [°C]	Peak area 1 [J.g ⁻¹]	Peak area 2 [J.g ⁻¹]	PA6 mass fraction
PA6	-	220	-	61.54	1
PA6/PP	163	220	50.73	29.44	0.48
Waste film	128.9	218	98.58	12.06	0.2

3.3 In-situ plasma treatment for enhanced melt impregnation

Subtle separation of fibres from the unsized CF tow (Figure 7a) can lead to pronounced fibre misalignment and eventual failure of the tape manufacturing process. Fibres entering the viscous melt in the impregnator tend to wash out, necessitating careful control of the fibre alignment in the dry tow. It was found that the tow was firmly bundled when the in-line plasma treatment was active (Figure 7b). This led to diminished fibre washout and eliminated spontaneous process failure. Improved tow cohesion and uniform alignment by plasma treatment are explained by the pneumatic spreading effect of the dry air flowing through the nozzle.

Figure 7: Images of the dry (a) as-received and (b) in-situ plasma surface treated CF tow passing between guiding pins leading to the melt impregnator.

3.4 Melt impregnated carbon fibre tape properties

After melt impregnation and hot-pin post-consolidation, at a fixed speed, the tape quality for the three matrix systems was assessed by cross-sectional microscopy, depicted in Figure 8. The tape dimensions changed for the various matrices. PA6 tapes (Figures 8a and 8b) were around 4.8 mm wide. PA6/PP (Figures 8c and 8d) and PA6/LLDPE (Figures 8e and 8f) tapes were wider, with widths of approximately 6.3 and 6.2 mm, respectively. Plasma surface treating the CF appears to have had an effect on the PA6/PP tape, where the width increased to approximately 7.3 mm. Overall, these results suggest that the plasma surface treatment has little effect on the tape dimensions.

Figure 8: Cross-sectional micrographs of composite tapes constituting (a) CF/PA6, (b) pCF/PA6, (c) CF/PA6/PP, (d) pCF/PA6/PP, (e) CF/rPA6/rLLDPE, and (f) pCF/rPA6/rLLDPE.

Blended polymeric matrices can shape intricate morphologies that strongly govern the composite performance [14]. Micro-scale cross-sectional images of fibre-reinforced PA6/PP and PA6/LLDPE tapes are illustrated in Figures 9a and 9b, respectively. Evidently, the PA6/PP composite, with a 50:50 wt.%, exhibits a co-continuous morphology. The heterogeneous dispersion is especially visible in resin-rich areas. Composites made from the waste film had a mixture ratio disparity (Section 3.1). Hence, it is expected that the LLDPE would form a continuous matrix phase with dispersed PA6 particles. However, the presence of PA6 particles is not easily observed in Figure 9b. It may be that the shredded PA6/LLDPE film did not melt-blend effectively in the single screw extruder, leading to distinct phases at a larger scale. The PA6-LLDPE mixture quality during extrusion and its effect on composite performance must be assessed in future work.

Figure 9: Cross-sectional micrographs of composite tapes constituting (a) CF/PA6/PP and (b) CF/PA6/LLDPE.

The cross-sectional images show that the melt impregnation die can produce high-quality tapes with PA6, PA6/PP, and PA6/LLDPE matrices. Compared to state-of-the-art powder and commingling impregnation processes, the introduced melt impregnator minimises intermediate processing steps, such as powderisation, powder dispersion, or filament drawing. The introduced process is also solvent-free. Everything considered, the plasma-enhanced melt impregnation process minimises environmental harm and processing complexity while facilitating the use of hard-to-recycle polymeric blends, as demonstrated with PA6/PP and PA6/LLDPE. It is a viable process to directly impregnate dry fibres with shredded waste polymer and easily integrates in-line fibre treatment.

3.5 Composite properties

Short beam strength of unidirectional fibre-reinforced samples is plotted in Figure 10. Plasma surface treating the CF statistically significantly increased the short beam strength for composites with PA6 and the PA6/PP matrices. For the first time, we show that in-line plasma surface treating CF increased the mean PA6 and PA6/PP matrix composite short beam strength by 45.2% and 89.8%, respectively. Importantly, the PA6/PP matrix composite made from as-received fibre failed by inelastic deformation (Figure 11). Plasma surface treating CF changed the composite failure to be caused by inelastic deformation and interlaminar shear. Plasma treatment had no effect on composites made from the hard-to-recycle film. These composites also had a significantly lower short beam strength compared to the PA6 and the PA6/PP matrix composites.

Figure 10: Short beam strength boxplots of unidirectional CF-reinforced (a) PA6, (b) PA6/PP, and (c) recycled PA6/LLDPE. The two-sample t-test statistical significance is indicated between as-received and plasma surface treated CF samples for the three matrix systems.

The short beam strength curves in Figure 11 show that plasma surface treating the CF significantly stiffened the PA6/PP matrix composite and altered the failure mode to inelastic and interlaminar shear. This can be explained by enhanced bonding between the functionalised pCF surface and PA6, constituting 50% of the matrix. Co-continuous PP in the matrix continues to bond poorly to the incompatible PA6 and the functionalised pCF. Composites made from the hard-to-recycle polymer failed inelastically. Plasma treatment had no statistically significant beneficial effect on these composites, suggesting that a higher PA6 content is needed for enhanced bonding with the polar pCF surface. This highlights that the surface functionality must be tailored to suit the polymeric matrix. In the case of PA6/LLDPE waste, the polar PA6 blended with dispersive LLDPE must be compatibilised, for instance, using maleic anhydride [15] or by plasma modifying the bulk polymer blend in a reactive extrusion process [4]. When both matrix constituents are polar, the interface can benefit from a 36% increase in O/C ratio on the CF surface (Section 3.1). Moreover, even if pCF-PA6 bonding is enhanced in the PA6/LLDPE (20:80 wt.%) composite, the small dispersed PA6 content in the LLDPE phase with a seven times lower Young's modulus leads to poor load transfer to the pCF and PA6. The combination of weak interfacial bonding and poor load transfer led to comparatively weak PA6/LLDPE matrix composite performance.

Figure 11: Short beam strength curves for as-received and plasma surface treated unidirectional CF-reinforced PA6/PP composite.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents two important contributions. Firstly, a novel slot-channel melt impregnation tool was used to produce CF-reinforced tapes from hard-to-recycle polymer blends found in the New Zealand waste stream. Namely, PA6/PP (50:50 wt.%), which was produced from virgin polymer, and

PA6/LLDPE (20:80 wt.%) waste film. Secondly, for the first time, an APPJ treatment was integrated to surface treat CF immediately prior to melt impregnation. During tape production, the in-line plasma treatment enhanced fibre alignment and cohesion in the tow by pneumatic spreading below the jet. As a result, process failures by fibre washout in the melt impregnator channel, which occasionally occurred with as-received fibre, were eliminated. This work demonstrated that increasing the CF surface O/C ratio by 36% leads to significantly enhanced fibre-matrix bonding in compression moulded composites made from melt-impregnated tapes containing primarily PA6. The CF surface treatment increased the mean PA6 and PA6/PP matrix composite short beam strength by 45.2% and 89.8%, respectively. The small PA6 content in the PA6/LLDPE matrix hindered significant composite performance enhancement by polar fibre functionalisation. Consequently, the dry air plasma surface treatment is not compatible with all matrix systems. Specifically, the dry air plasma-modified CF surface is highly compatible with the polar PA6 but remains incompatible with dispersive LLDPE. Hence, a compatibilisation process of the blend is needed for improved composite performance when the dispersive matrix constituent is dominant. Overall, the introduced slot-channel melt impregnation process effectively produces fibre-reinforced hard-to-recycle polymer tapes while minimising additional processing steps that are needed in powder or commingling impregnation. Plasma surface modifying the reinforcement effectively strengthened interfacial adhesion with polar matrix constituents.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Office of the Prime Minister's Chief Science Advisor. Rethinking Plastics in Aotearoa New Zealand, 2021 [online]: <https://www.pmcsa.ac.nz/topics/rethinking-plastics/>
- [2] Royal Society of New Zealand, Plastics in the Environment: Te Ao Hurihuri – The Changing World, Royal Society of New Zealand, 2021 [online]: <https://www.royalsociety.org.nz/what-we-do/our-expert-advice/all-expert-advice-papers/plastics-in-the-environment-evidence-summary/>
- [3] Gall, Markus, Freudenthaler, Paul J, Fisher, Joerg, Lang, Reinhold W, "Characterization of Composition and Structure–Property Relationships of Commercial Post-Consumer Polyethylene and Polypropylene Recyclates," *Polymers*, no. 10, pp. 1574, 2021.
- [4] Ashraf, Jesna, Bertin, Maicon, Verbeek, Casparus Johannes Reinhard, "Plasma-induced reactive compatibilization of polypropylene/polyamide 6 blends," *ACS Applied Polymer Materials*, vol 7, pp. 641-653, 2025
- [5] Xanthos, M, Narth, KA, "Product design with glass fiber reinforced polymer blends, with potential applications in recycling," *Polymer Composites*, vol. 19, issue 6, pp. 768-780, 2004
- [6] Plastics Europe, 2023. Plastics – the fast Facts 2023. *Plastics Europe* [online]: <https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/plastics-the-fast-facts-2023/>
- [7] Ho, Kingsley KC, Adam F. Lee, Steven Lamoriniere, and Alexander Bismarck, "Continuous atmospheric plasma fluorination of carbon fibres," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 364-373, 2008.
- [8] Xie, Jianfei, Danwei Xin, Hongyan Cao, Cuntao Wang, Yi Zhao, Lan Yao, Feng Ji, and Yiping Qiu, "Improving carbon fiber adhesion to polyimide with atmospheric pressure plasma treatment," *Surface and coatings technology*, vol. 206, no. 2-3, pp. 191-201, 2011.
- [9] Xiao, Jianqi, Xuejun Zhang, Zehua Zhao, Jie Liu, Qiufei Chen, and Xiaoxu Wang, "Rapid and continuous atmospheric plasma surface modification of PAN-based carbon fibers," *ACS omega*, vol. 7, no. 13, pp. 10963-10969, 2022.

- [10] Moosburger-Will, Judith, et al., "Methyltrimethoxysilane plasma polymerization coating of carbon fiber surfaces," *Surface & Coatings Technology*, vol. 311, pp. 223-230, 2017.
- [11] Pitto, Maximilian, Fiedler, Holger, Kim, Nam Kyeun, Verbeek, Casparus Johannes Reinhard, Allen, Tom David, Bickerton, Simon, "Carbon fibre surface modification by plasma for enhanced polymeric composite performance: A review," *Composites Part A*, vol. 180, 2024.
- [12] Pitto, Maximilian, Fiedler, Holger, Verbeek, Casparus Johannes Reinhard, Allen, Tom David, Bickerton, Simon, "High-power air plasma diagnostics by optical emission spectroscopy for subsecond continuous carbon fibre surface treatment," *Composites Part A*, vol. 193, 2025.
- [13] Camargo, Mariangela, Forte, Maria Madalena Camargo, Wolf, Carlos Rodolfo, "Linear low density polyethylene thermal fractions by DSC technique," *International Journal of Polymer Analysis and Characterization*, vol. 13, pp. 49-65, 2007.
- [14] Trongsatikul, Tatiya, Chaiwong, Saowapa, "In situ fibre-reinforced composite films of poly(lactic acid)/low-density polyethylene blends: effects of composition on morphology, transport and mechanical properties," *Polymer International*, vol. 66, pp. 1419-1683, 2017.
- [15] Cao, Jiandong, Liu, Hailiang, Chen, Qinjia, Bai, Yangxiao, "Enhancing the interfacial properties of polyethylene-based carbon fiber composites through low-temperature thermally reduced graphene," *Fibers and Polymers*, vol. 24, pp. 4823-4830, 2024.